

EMERGING ISSUES IN ACCOUNTING EDUCATION AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

Idris Benuh Adama, Ph.D.

Department of Business Education (Accounting Unit), Federal University of Education, Kontagora, Nigeria

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20507832>

ABSTRACT: Accounting education is crucial to socioeconomic development of every nation due to variety of economic information it provides. Also, sustainable development has become very important globally following the need to achieve sustainable economic growth; therefore, every nation, organization and profession has roles to play in achieving this sustainable development, In the light of this, this paper explored emerging issues in accounting education and sustainable development in Nigeria. Qualitative method was employed for the study by reviewing extant literature on accounting education, entrepreneurship, disruptive technologies and sustainable development. The findings revealed that technological challenges brought on by artificial intelligence and cyber security affect accounting education. In conclusion, accounting education has been identified as an important field of study and relevant as panacea in the Nigerian sustainable development. It is recommended that accounting curriculum should be restructured to ensure that entrepreneurship is emphasized in core areas in accounting education and Accountants need to be well-versed in current economic and technological changes in order to be effective and remain relevant in the ever-changing environment.

KEYWORDS: Accounting, Accounting Education, Disruptive Technologies, Entrepreneurship and Sustainable Development.

1INTRODUCTION

Emerging issues are a major considerations that must be taken into account when discussing sustainable development vis-à-vis accounting education. For purpose of this study, incorporating entrepreneurship development in the curriculum of accounting education and adoption of disruptive technologies in teaching and learning of accounting in tertiary institutions for enhancing sustainable development in Nigeria are looked at.

Nigeria as a nation is characterized with high rate of unemployment and this result into a lot of vices ranging from insecurity, kidnapping and poverty, among others. It is also observed that so many qualified graduates are roaming around the country searching for jobs due to the fact that tertiary institutions produce graduates without considering the economy, the needs of the people and the society or the curriculum content which does not contain much of entrepreneurial education which entails self-reliance and self-employment.

On the contrary, over time, accounting education has been very pivotal in determining the quality of accounting profession, and in line with this, Zhang, Dai and Vasarhelyi (2018) stated that the rate of change in technology

continually disrupts traditional processes in every area of life, including accounting. Therefore, accounting education will not be an exception in this Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) age. Furthermore, Zhang, *et al* (2018) also revealed that most of the students who graduated from the traditional accounting programmes do not possess the skills and knowledge required by businesses, particularly in enterprises that require high-level automation and Artificial Intelligence (AI), therefore creating a mismatch.

Disruptive technology is presently taking the world by storm, relating this to accounting, Gould (2017) asserted that accounting profession is radically changing, driven by disruptive technology and changing practices. Also, according to Ibrahim, Sallha and Rashid (2020), disruptive technology arose as a result of the progress of Big Data, AI and Cloud. More so, Corporate Finance Institute (CFI) (2022) gave examples of disruptive technology to include: Online news sites and platforms, E-learning, AI, Internet of Things (IoT), Block chain, Robotic Process Automations (RPA), E-commerce, Advanced Analytics, Ride-Sharing Apps, GPS Systems.

However, with specific professional skills and involvement in governance, risk management, business analysis, decision support, due diligence, anticorruption activities and ensuring corporate transparency, professional accountants today are reassessing their roles because of the sustainable development goals (SDGs) and corporate sustainability. Importance of accounting activates in SDGs achievement is recognized by professional international organizations, among them are International Federation of Accountants (IFAC), the Association of Chartered Certified Accountants (ACCA), the Intergovernmental Working Group of Experts on International Standards of Accounting and Reporting Council (ISAR) and the World Business Forum on Sustainable Development.

More so, globalization has significantly altered the conditions within which accountants function as well as the entrepreneurial activities which they get involved in (Gould, 2017). Accountants who are practicing accounting profession have contributed towards the achievement of sustainable development, since the goal of sustainable development is to provide inclusive growth, economic prosperity and social transformation for everyone by 2030.

Several researchers have studied e-learning and education like Osuji and Nwoke (2019), Olutola and Olatoye (2018), Ajegbomogun, Okunlaya and Alawiye (2017), Islam and Selim (2006) but there is a gap in knowledge on studies on disruptive technologies such as e-learning, Artificial Intelligence (AI) Guided learning, Chat-Based collaboration and accounting education amidst issues and challenges of non-inclusion of entrepreneurship development in accounting curricula in tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Therefore, this study explores the nexus between accounting education, entrepreneurship, disruptive technologies and sustainable development in Nigeria. However, the methodology adopted is purely content analysis that is literatures were reviewed on accounting and accounting education, entrepreneurship development, disruptive technologies and sustainable development.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATIONS

Concept of Accounting and Accounting Education

Oluwatuyi, Ibrahim and Folayan (2022) defined accounting as the process of identifying, measuring, and presenting economic data to allow consumers to make informed decisions. Accounting involves measuring, sharing, and analysis of financial activities (Agbo, 2023). Accounting is also defined as the process of documenting, categorizing, and summarizing in a meaningful way and in terms of financial transactions, events, and transactions that are at least partially of a financial nature and analyzing the outcome thereof (American Institute of Certified Public Accounts, AICPA 1975)

Agbo (2023) further stated that accounting is the process of measuring and identifying economic variables in particular organizations and disseminating information based on this measurement to users who need to make informed decisions. Ibrahim (2009) sees accounting in a variety of perspectives, including as a task carried out by accountants and their substitutes, a system made up of numerous interconnected and interdependent pieces, a management approach and a field of study. Also, the term accounting is defined by Woods (2019) as the systematic and detailed recording of monetary transactions of an entity.

Herein, accounting is referred to be a means of communication for businesses that reflects the economic and social development of a nation. It is viewed as a tool for both macroeconomic and social regulation. However, the scope of accounting covers: Financial Accounting; Auditing; Management Accounting; Performance Management; Financial Management; Taxation; Forensic Accounting; Auditing; Public Sector Accounting, Social and Environmental Accounting.

Accounting education on the other hand is the transfer of knowledge of standards and principles of accounting to individuals (Okafor, 2012). Also, Nwokike (2019) stated that accounting education is the type of education that provides individuals with skills and knowledge in accounting, computing and data processing occupations for gainful employment in private and public enterprises or for self-employment. Accounting education is one of the vocational education courses offered in Nigeria tertiary institutions for career in accounting and education.

Ugwu, Ezeabii and Ugwunwoti (2020) opined that accounting education helps students to learn to become professional accountants. Therefore, their professionalism will lead them to establish accounting firms that would create employment opportunities for sustainable development. It provides individuals opportunity for the acquisition of relevant skills, abilities and competences both mental and physical equipment for the individual to live in and contribute to the development of the nation. Accounting education is a programme of studies in the higher institution of learning, such as colleges of education, polytechnics and universities.

For this study, accounting education is conceptualized as the process of teaching and learning accounting in colleges of education, polytechnics and universities in Nigeria.

Concept of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship development is the process of enhancing entrepreneurial skills and knowledge through structured training and institution building programmes. Fasae and Alabi (2021) defined entrepreneurship as a means by which one no longer waits to see who will give him a job, but rather seizes the opportunity to secure his future and in the process creates job and livelihood for others.

The real essence of entrepreneurship education is to ensure the improvement of educational quality by equipping the young ones with basic skills that will make them functional and productive in the society (Enu, 2012). Fasae and Alabi (2021) further stated that universities are centres of learning which have always been places where the skills and knowledge of students are chiseled to suit the requirements and structure courses in a way that will help their students or graduates to be gainfully employed in the labour market.

Concept of Disruptive Technology

Disruptive technology (DT) creates an entirely new industry or product by displacing conventional technology (Ogunode & Abubakar, 2020). According to Dawsey (2022), five (5) disruptive technologies in education are online learning (o-Learning), Artificial Intelligence (AI) Guided learning, Chat-Based collaboration, Virtual and Augmented Reality (VR and AR). E-learning is disrupting conventional classroom learning (U-EENI, 2022). Hence, DT is conceptualized in this study as that technological innovation that majorly changes the processes, procedures or methods enterprises, institutions and industries operate their affairs.

Concept of Sustainable Development

Sustainable development is the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Sustainable development has been described as that development that meets the needs and aspirations of the present generations, without compromising the ability to meet the need of future generations (Agbata, Okaro & Onyeogubalu, 2022). Furthermore, sustainable development strategy connotes the capacity to improve the quality of human life while living within the carrying capacity of the supporting ecosystem (Ironkwe & Success, 2017).

Also, Oduma (2012) defined sustainable development has concept that has to do with meeting the needs of the present and future generation without denying access to the same natural resources for their own requirement. Akpan (2022) emphasized that development is regarded where it readily conjures up images of roads, modern building, electricity supplies, a good telecommunication network and other symbols of physical development.

Technological Challenges of Accounting

Trends in information and communication technology are progressively changing the way people communicate and interact; and how firms conduct business operations, record transactions, and store, retrieve and share business-related information (Ateke & Nwulu, 2018). Many aspects of personal, social and commercial lives, including everyday decision-making, are increasingly influenced by the internet and internet-enabled technologies (Ateke & Lawson, 2020). Advances in technology have significantly altered the way business

activities are conducted and how records of business activities are captured, stored, retrieved and disseminated (Ateke & Isaac, 2020).

However, technology has posed challenges to how business is conducted, and how records of business operations are captured, stored, retrieved and disseminated (Ojukwu & Chukwudi-Ofoedu, 2023). Herein, this paper identifies and briefly explains two major challenges in terms of automation and artificial intelligence, and cyber security.

Automation and Artificial Intelligence (AI)

One of the major technological issues facing accounting is artificial intelligence (AI) (Onwughai, 2022). However, Grewal (2014) stated that AI is a mechanical simulation system that involves gathering, evaluating, and eventually sending knowledge, information, and intelligence to appropriate parties in the form of intelligence that may be used. Zemánková (2019) defined AI as a system's capacity to efficiently receive external input, learn from it, and apply what it has learned to fulfill specific goals and tasks through flexible adaptation.

Adoption of AI in accounting also reduces fraud, improves accuracy of accounting data, and encourages reform of traditional accounting (Chukwuani & Egiyi, 2020). Also, in the view of Mohammad (2020), accountants will ultimately be able to reduce accounting costs and contribute value to the accounting by reorienting their attention away from the dreary duties they are currently performing and toward judgments that are based on data and analytics.

However, AI poses challenge to accountants, which include high initial installation costs, the displacement of human labour, and the inability of computers to fully function without human involvement because they lack human initiative, empathy, and decision-making skills (Fogarty, 2019). Hasan (2022) stated that employment of AI has a number of disadvantages, some of which may be detrimental to the accounting profession.

Cyber Security

Sanni, Adegoke, Abu and Ojo (2023) opined that accounting faces many challenges, including cyber security, which has grown increasingly difficult as technology has developed. Cyber security is the process of securing the networks, systems, and applications of digital networks. All information assets, whether they are in physical copy or digital form, are assumed to be protected by IT security. The Information Assurance (IA) component of a cyber-security system entails safeguarding information and managing risks related to its use, processing, storage, and transfer, as well as the systems and procedures that employ it (Wang, Kannan & Ulmer, 2013). Cyber security is the biggest issue facing accountants right now since unauthorized access to a country's data base can have a detrimental effect on that nation's socioeconomic development (Ehioghiren, Ojeaga & Eneh, 2021).

Furthermore, today's accounting-related technologies include e-business input and output processing equipment, cloud computing, information technology, supply chain management systems, forensic accounting equipment (Bille, 2022). The use of technology in accounting has improved a number of processes, although, there are also

disadvantages in the technologies becoming obsolete, therefore, regular updates are necessary for accounting systems to function properly and effectively as a tool for socioeconomic growth (Quinto II, 2022). The system's increased updating expenses could have a negative effect on profitability. Financial data loss could also result if proper backup strategies are not adopted (Armenia & Stefano, 2021).

There are several infrastructural challenges in tertiary institutions in Nigeria, however the challenges in focus here are ICT equipment and e-learning enabling gadgets such as laptops, desktops, accounting software for training the students, internet subscriptions, power supply, problem of inaccessibility of telecom services in some areas where tertiary institutions are located, poor or no intra-connectivity of the faculties and departments with the institutions central ICT facilities. Students and lecturers also suffer some personal infrastructural challenges that can hinder effective e-learning usage such as: high cost of data to use the internet; high cost of hand-held mobile devices such as smart phones, palmtops and their accessories and security of their personal e-learning gadgets (Agada, 2018).

Accounting and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

The important roles played by the accounting profession in building study and sustainable economic and financial markets are enshrined in SDGs 4, 8, and 16. SDG 4 is on quality and accessibility of education. According to Herath and Lim (2019), SDG 4 recognizes pertinent and affordable education which assists in alleviating poverty as well as in promoting economic development. Thus, the accounting professional bodies support this through high quality education and training for capacity building of their members so that they can be competent in meeting and satisfying societal and economic demands. SDG 8 is on decent work and economic growth. Chartered Global Management Accountants – CGMA and Association of International Certified Professional Accountants – AICPA (2018) provided that Accountants are highly connected to prosperity and enhanced standard of living. They play significant roles in institutional and architectural intensification which will enhance societal lives, especially in developing nations such as Nigeria. SDG 16 is on good governance and advocacy for peace, justice, and strong institutions.

Furthermore, Herath and Lim (2019) as well as CGMA and AICPA (2018) stated that the ethical, governance, and professional standards of the accounting profession enable the accountants to contribute to sustainable businesses, good capital markets, better management of public funds, and delivery of public services which will enhance sustainable development. In Nigeria, accounting professional bodies, that is, the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN) and Association of National Accountants of Nigeria (ANAN) foster these by constantly addressing matters relating to governance, corruption, fraud, and improper accounting and auditing practices.

CONCLUSION

The study looks into the need to inculcate entrepreneurship consciousness into accounting education students in tertiary institutions in Nigeria by way of providing practical experiences, which will, by no small means, increase self-sustainability of accounting education graduates and reduce unemployment in the country and

thereby reducing many social vices that are currently ravaging the nation. Also, in the absence of a well-developed accounting process that can keep up with emerging technology, there would unavoidably be under and incorrect resource allocation that will negatively impact sustainable development. Accounting education has been identified as an important field of study which is relevant as panacea to the Nigerian sustainable development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations have been identified and deemed necessary:

1. The accounting curriculum should be restructured to ensure that entrepreneurship is emphasized in core areas in accounting education.
2. Tertiary institutions should provide entrepreneurship centres where students can have practical experiences that will quicken the consciousness in them.
3. Accountants need to be well-versed in current economic and technological changes in order to be effective and remain relevant in the ever-changing environment. The provision of adequate e-learning equipment should be made available to teachers as this will go a long way to maintain effectiveness in their teaching process.

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